

Trace Determination of Zinc by Differential Pulse Polarography

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ZINC has been determined by many method and references of its analysis by X-ray fluorescence¹, neutron activation analysis² and atomic absorption spectroscopy³ are found in literature; and among sensitive techniques are anodic stripping voltammetry⁴, differential pulse polarography⁵, differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetry⁶ and a.c. voltammetry⁷.

In the present work, differential pulse polarographic method for the determination of zinc at ppb level has been developed. It has been possible to determine zinc in coal ash and in A.R. grade ammonium chloride. Simultaneous determination Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} can also be achieved.

Experimental

The polarographic measurements were made on a Metrohm Polarecord E-506 instrument. The electrode system used was DME as a working electrode, Ag/AgCl as a reference electrode and Pt-electrode as an auxiliary electrode. The sample was deaerated by bubbling nitrogen through the solution.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solutions were made in tripple distilled water. A stock solution of Zn^{2+} (50 $\mu g/\mu l$) was prepared by dissolving suitable quantity of $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$.

Procedure: Total volume of the system was maintained at 25 ml. 1 M $NH_4Cl + NH_4OH$ buffer (2.5 ml) was taken in the polarography cell and volume made upto 25 ml with TDW. To it was added Zn^{2+} standard solution and the polarogram recorded. All measurements were made against a blank. The instrumental settings were as follows: scan range, 0.0 – 1.5 V; scan rate, 6 $mV s^{-1}$; mm/tdp, 1.0; tdp, 1.0; A/mm, 1×10^{-9} , pulse amplitude, 5 mV.

Results and Discussion

Selection of supporting medium: Various buffers, neutral electrolytes, organic acids, alkali and pyridine were studied for this purpose. 0.1 M KNO_3 , 0.1 M KCl , 0.1 M acetate buffer, 0.1 M $KCl + 0.1 M$ pyridine gave large peak heights. But in $NH_4Cl + NH_4OH$ medium, Zn^{2+} gave largest

and symmetrical peak with evenly rising pulse steps. For concentrations greater than 0.5 M each of NH_4Cl and NH_4OH , distorted Zn^{2+} peak was obtained. Also, with decreasing NH_4OH concentration, reduction in diffusion current was observed. The lowest buffer concentration at which Zn^{2+} showed maximum pulse current was 0.1 M $NH_4Cl + 0.1 M$ NH_4OH and was chosen for further studies.

Effect of maximum suppressors: For Zn^{2+} concentrations greater than 5 ppm, a maximum was observed at -1.216 V. The effect of addition of gelatin, bromophenol blue, methyl red, Triton X-100 as suppressors was studied in the range $1 \times 10^{-5} - 10 \times 10^{-3} \%$. The effectiveness of suppressor was seen by recording DC polarograms as well, in which the presence or absence of maximum could be distinctly seen. Out of the four suppressors, gelatin, bromophenol blue and Triton X-100 eliminated the maximum at 4×10^{-5} , 1×10^{-4} and $1 \times 10^{-3} \%$ concentrations, respectively. In the presence of $1 \times 10^{-3} \%$ methyl red, Zn^{2+} polarogram showed no distinct maximum but the peak was not very symmetrical. However, the maximum was observed in the DC polarogram. The concentration of bromophenol blue required to eliminate the maximum was least ($1 \times 10^{-4} \%$) as compared to other suppressors; Triton X-100 was chosen because of the appreciably larger pulse height. Therefore, for Zn^{2+} concentrations greater than 5 ppm, $1 \times 10^{-3} \%$ Triton X-100 was used.

Calibration plot: Current-concentration relation was found to be linear for 20 ppb to 8 ppm Zn^{2+} . For concentrations greater than 5 ppm, $1 \times 10^{-3} \%$ Triton X-100 was used to eliminate the maximum. Calibration graphs were obtained in three concentration ranges: 20–100 ppb, 0.1–1 ppm and 1–8 ppm. The recording parameters were changed appropriately for measuring lower concentrations of Zn^{2+} . Suitable blank correction was also made. Lowest determinable concentration of Zn^{2+} by the given method was 20 ppb.

Effect of other ions: The effect of the presence of some cations was studied for 1 ppm Zn^{2+} determination. Al^{3+} is electroinactive in the given medium and is, therefore, tolerated in large concentrations. As^{3+} gave ill-defined wave but could be tolerated upto 1:300; Cu^{2+} was tolerated upto 1:15, but at higher ratios led to irregularity in polarogram. Tl^{+} could be tolerated in large concentrations, and Cd^{2+} upto 1:200. Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and V^{5+} were tolerated in the ratios 1:10 and 1:1, respectively. However, Co^{2+} and Cr^{3+} interfered.

Precision and accuracy: Analysis of 10 solutions of 1 ppm Zn^{2+} in ammonium buffer gave mean pulse height in nA as 23.58 ± 0.45 (mean deviation). The standard deviation was 0.61.

Application studies †

Zinc in AR ammonium chloride : A 1 M solution of AR NH_4Cl was prepared in triple-distilled water. From this solution, 2.5, 5.0 and 7.5 ml were used as the supporting medium alongwith 0.1 N NH_4OH . The effective NH_4Cl concentration in 25 ml system was 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 M. The change in NH_4Cl concentration from 0.1 to 0.5 M in 25 ml system does not effect the Zn^{2+} peak. Polarograms were recorded, and by standard addition method the amount of Zn^{2+} in NH_4Cl was calculated. Pulse current read off the calibration plots gave results in accordance with the standard addition calculations. Ammonium chloride was found to contain 0.001 1% Zn^{2+} .

Leachable zinc in coal ash : Coal ash samples (obtained from Coal Survey Laboratory, Nagpur) were analysed for Zn^{2+} . A weighed quantity of coal ash was digested with concentrated HCl (10 ml) till complete silica was precipitated. After cooling, the white precipitate of silica was filtered off. The filtrate was taken up with water and made upto 10 ml. The polarogram of different aliquots of the sample solution was recorded against a blank. Qualitative and quantitative evaluation was done by standard addition procedure as well as by the calibration plot. The results were found to agree with both the methods. Three coal ash samples from three different regions were analysed, which were found to contain 2.9, 0.82 and 1.85 mg Zn^{2+} /kg.

Simultaneous determination of Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} : Simultaneous determination was done in a synthetic mixture with the set polarographic conditions. A minimum of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of metal ion could be simultaneously determined with high precision.

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Ultra-trace Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper using 2-Thioquinaldinanilide

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THE reagent, 2-thioquinaldinanilide (TQA) has been utilised to develop a simple and rapid micro-chemical method for the detection and direct ultra-trace (ppb) determination of copper by spectrophotometry¹. The reagent is almost specific for copper in presence of almost all the metal ions. The method leaves no other choice for its wide range of applications towards a number of synthetic mixtures of composite form and standard samples with minimum deviation.

This newly synthesised reagent (TQA) offered several advantages over those proposed earlier²⁻⁵. High stability and easy solubility of the reagent in organic solvents, routine rapidity, wide pH and optimum range, and great interference limit with high selectivity are some of the major important highlights of the present method.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells were used for absorbance measurements. pH of the solutions were measured room temperature (27°) with a Elico LI-10 pH meter having all purpose glass electrodes.

A 0.1% (w/v) TQA¹ solution in ethanol was used. A 10% (w/v) triethanolamine hydrochloride (A.R.) was prepared. A buffer solution of pH 2.7 was prepared using sodium acetate—hydrochloric acid mixture. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their soluble salts and were standardised by conventional procedures. AnalaR grade solvents were used directly.

Procedure : To an appropriate amount of standard copper sulphate (10–100 μg cu) solution in a 25 ml standard volumetric flask was added a few drops of very dilute hydrochloric acid followed by 0.1% TQA solution (5 ml) and pure ethanol (7.5 ml) (pH 2.7), and the solution was diluted to 25 ml with water. Measure the absorbance of the blue-violet complex at 550 nm against water blank. Reagent blank prepared under identical conditions showed no absorbance, at this wave length. The unknown solution was processed similarly and its concentration was determined from the calibration curve.

Determination of copper in presence of V^{5+} , Mo^{6+} and W^{6+} : To a Cu^{2+} (0.1 mg) solution was